

Summary of recommendation

Maintain login-free access to the NEON Data Portal to support more and better research centered on NEON, and continue to engage with a diverse set of researchers. If necessary use rate limits and loosening of these limits via authorization to manage challenges related to large data downloads.

Justification

Open data is a core component of NEON's mission. Making this data fully open and accessible is essential to the broad use of this data and the adoption of the observatory as a central component of ecological research in the coming decades. While NEON user accounts can provide a lot of value (e.g., storing searches, submitting questions about data, requesting assignable assets), they should not be required for access to NEON data for the following reasons:

1. **Requiring creation of accounts will result in decreased use of NEON data.** With each small increase in effort required to engage with open resources, the number and diversity of people willing to engage decreases substantially. Keeping the activation energy for engaging with NEON data low will increase the number of people who use it.
2. **Support external tool development that improves and increases usage.** Fully leveraging open data often requires the use of external tools. Large ecosystems of software tools have been developed to support the use of open data including NEON data (e.g., <https://www.neonscience.org/resources/code-resources>). These tools typically rely on being able to access the data without authorization so that any user can quickly and easily start using them and the associated data. While tools can be designed to handle authorization (e.g., through the use of API keys) this requires additional time investment by the tool developers and presents additional complexity for new users, potentially reducing both tool development and adoption.
3. **Maintain the NEON Data Portal as the single definitive authorized source for NEON data.** Because direct access to data is essential for reproducibility and external tool development, requiring authorization to access openly licensed data will lead to reposting of the data by users and data being accessed through these secondary sources. This will decrease usage statistics measured by NEON making it difficult to measure and communicate the breadth of the data usage and is scientifically problematic because secondary data sources are often not updated when fixes and improvements to data are made at the primary source.
4. **Support reproducible access to data:** Reproducing past analyses is difficult even when code or executable notebooks are openly shared. As modern research relies on numerous software packages in a single analysis, even a small breaking change in a single dependency can make it impossible to rerun the analysis without a laborious examination of the code. Studies have shown that the extent to which code can be

rebuilt with reasonable effort is quite low (less than 20%) (Collberg et al 2014). So it is important that authorization for open data not add yet another point of failure for the reproducibility and integrity of analyses using NEON data.

5. **Compliance with privacy policies** The collection and storage of personally identifiable information such as names and email addresses will require compliance with a myriad of international privacy policies such as GDPR and the recently passed California Privacy Act, CCPA. The policies and management of such systems will place an additional burden on NEON infrastructure and staff.

There are two standard arguments for requiring authorization to access open data that can be addressed while still avoiding authorization:

1. **Need to understand and measure usage.** Measuring usage of data is essential to it being fully valued and credited by the scientific community. However, as described above, requiring authorization is likely to both reduce usage and make it more difficult to measure. Fortunately measuring the key aspects of usage does not require authorization. Total downloads, usage by specific universities, and general user characteristics can all be obtained using conventional web analytics approaches. However, the most important aspects of usage for projects like NEON are not downloads, but the resulting scientific products. NEON already has a well designed system for citing individual data products to allow for automated measurement of their use by the community in publications and other research products. Further tracking of scientific products could be encouraged by providing a website where users developing products based on NEON data can provide information on those products for broader sharing among the community. NEON should engage with existing efforts including Make Data Count (<https://makedatacount.org/>) to develop and improve methods for tracking usage that do not impede access to data.
2. **Need to manage bandwidth when distributing large amounts of data.** With large amounts of data there are sometimes issues with needing to ensure that large bandwidth transfers are actively managed. The need for restrictions should be balanced against restricted use based on reduced external tool development and usage. If still deemed necessary this can be implemented using a combination of rate limits and API keys. Rate limits on downloads will allow tools and pipelines to run without authorization, but slowly. Users can then create an account and obtain an API key to reduce or remove the rate limits. For high volume users this will be an acceptable inconvenience, while not obstructing the usage of the majority of users.

Source of community input

This input was developed by a group of open data leaders and NEON users listed below. If engagement with these ideas from a broader group of stakeholders is desired we would be happy to post this openly and solicit feedback and support more broadly.

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